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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a report of the implementation of the four participatory actions carried out in Barcelona, Rimini, Bratislava and Skopje, according to the plans described in Deliverable 3.1 “Participatory Actions”. The following participatory actions have been carried out:

- **Barcelona: A pedagogic experience with co-housing, from October 2013 thru January 2014.** The purpose of the action has been to develop design methods and tools to foster the participation of dwellers in the design process of their future homes. It was jointly carried out by students and tutors of the School of Architecture La Salle and members of the housing cooperative Sostre Civic.

- **Rimini: Defining strategies to facilitate access to social housing in a medium-size city, from June 2014 to March 2015.** The purpose of this action was to define possible and feasible strategies to support solutions for the social housing problems in a medium-size city. These strategies have to be proposed through an integrated approach involving the participation of public and private bodies in the action. These actions have been jointly carried out by Heriscape and the Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini.

- **Bratislava: Urban walk in the Zemník area, from March 2016 to June 2016.** The purpose of this activity was to organise an urban walk with the aim of fostering the participation of stakeholders in the development of the Zemník area, in the Danube riverfront. This work was carried out by the city of Bratislava and involved experts from the, municipality, residents, general public, community associations and organizations with an interest in the development.

- **Skopje: A community action in Ilinden. From 15 to 17 October 2015.** The goal of this participatory action was to foster the collaboration between the dwellers of the Ilinden neighbourhood in Skopje and students of architecture in the analysis of the living patterns. The work was conducted with the participation of students from the Faculty of Architecture, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, and the Faculty of Architecture, Polis University, Tirana.

The activities have been disseminated through various local media. A summary of the activities has been published in the [OIKONET Community Participation](#) blog. A video reporting the work done in each action has been produced and it is available in the OIKONET website.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

This document presents the work carried out in the four participatory actions carried out during the OIKONET project in Barcelona (Spain), Rimini (Italy), Bratislava (Slovakia) and Skopje (Macedonia). The activities have been implemented in accordance with the plans described in Deliverable 3.1 “Participatory Actions”. The knowledge and experience gained in the design and implementation of these community action projects can be of value to the OIKONET partners involved in the sub-networks Housing Research and Pedagogical Activities as well as to those actively involved with action research, citizen participation and community building processes (researchers, teachers, local administrations, social organizations).

2.2 Contribution of partners

The participatory action in Barcelona has been a joint initiative of the School of Architecture La Salle and Sostre Cívic. The action in Rimini involves Heriscape and the Ordine degli Architetti, Rimini, as well as number of local organizations. In the participatory action in Bratislava is an initiative of the city of Bratislava. Finally, the action in Skopje is a project of the University Ss. Cyril and Methodius, Macedonia, with the participation of lecturers from the University of Belgrade, Serbia; and Polis University, in Tirana, Albania.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The work carried out in the participatory activities was expected to have an educational impact on non-academic stakeholders. In this regard, it shared some of the objectives with the activities carried out in the sub-network Pedagogical Activities (WP4). Some of the issues addressed in these actions –such as housing regeneration, communication between professionals and non-professionals, place making and codesign, private and public collaboration and participatory planning– are also related to the work done in the sub-network Housing Research (see Deliverable 2.4 “Research matrix”). Along with the participatory actions, a series of dissemination activities were conducted at the local level which contribute to the objectives of Deliverable 7.3 “Local Media”.

3 BARCELONA: A PEDAGOGIC EXPERIENCE WITH CO-HOUSING

3.1 Introduction

A participatory action was carried out by the School of Architecture La Salle and the association of Sostre Cívic from October 2013 to January 2014, in Barcelona. The purpose of this activity was to develop design methods and tools to foster the participation of dwellers in the design process of their future homes. This work was carried out by architecture students participating in an elective seminar dedicated to the OIKONET project. Later, the methods and tools were implemented in two participatory sessions with members of the cooperative.

This chapter describes the structure of the learning activities carried out in the seminar and the results obtained. The learning activities have been carried out on in the learning space “[Civic Housing](#)” implemented in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces environment.

3.2 Learning Activities

3.2.1 Reflecting on the importance of citizen participation in architecture

The aim of the first phase of the seminar was to introduce students to the topic of participation in architecture and urban planning. This was done by analysing previous applications of participatory design processes and its underlying theoretical models, such as Bakema’s elements of transition, Smithson’s signs of occupancy, Alexander’s pattern language and De Carlo’s participatory design.

Lectures:

On October 4, 2013, Dr. Leandro Madrazo, professor from the School of Architecture La Salle, lectured on the topic “The multiple dimensions of housing”.

On October 9, 2013, Dr. Omayra Rivera, professor from the University of Puerto Rico, gave an on-line lecture on the topic “[Participatory methods of communication](#)” (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1. Prof. Omayra Rivera’s on-line lecture

Task 1: Why participation?

The task consisted in the identification of research topics concerning contemporary housing that were related with participation. The objective of the task was to find out why participation plays an important role in it.

- Deliverables

An A3 sheet summarizing the topic of research and explaining the need for architects to foster participation.

3.2.2 Designing a participatory process: methods and tools

The purpose of this activity was to design a participatory process. Different models of participatory processes exist, which are based on dialogue (exchange of information and negotiation among participants), observation (extracting behavioural patterns of people in living spaces) or in both. Whatever the model is, a fundamental issue is the use of appropriate means of representation to facilitate communication between professionals and non-professionals, between architects and dwellers.

Task 2: Participatory Methods of Communication

The objective of this activity was to identify and explain methods of communication that can help to foster a dialogue between professionals and dwellers. Students have analysed some of the communication tools and methods used in participatory processes. The goal was to understand and explain the methods (e.g. assumptions, purposes, processes), to document and explain with examples how participatory methods have been applied (objectives, outcomes) and to assess the value of the results obtained, through participation.

Deliverables

A3 sheets describing the analysis of the precedents.

Task 3: Design Participatory Methods of Communication

The objective of this task was to propose a methodology to communicate with the dwellers, including the design of the activities to be carried out and their implementation in participatory sessions.

Deliverables

An A3 sheet summarizing the proposed strategy, methods and techniques to foster communication with dwellers. (Figure 3.2)

Figure 3.2. An example of a communication methodology proposed by students

Implementation of the participatory process: first joint working session

The communication tools and participatory process devised in the previous activities were implemented in a participatory session that took place at the premises of Sostre Cívic in Barcelona on October 29, 2013. Forty members of the association and ten students participated in this session (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3. First participatory session

The aim of this first session was to understand the visions that participants had about their future dwelling. From an academic point of view, this activity enabled students to apply the participatory models and communication tools devised in the seminar. From the dwellers' point of view, this action represented the starting point of the design process of their future home.

The activities that dwellers carried out in this session were the following:

- **Activity 1.** 'DESCRIBE the space you live in'. Dwellers were inquired about their previous experience about their current living environment. They were asked to describe, with their own words, what they like most and least about their living places and write it in post-its to share it with the rest of participants (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4. Activity 1. ‘Describe Your Experience’

- **Activity 2.** ‘IMAGINE your ideal living space’. Participants were asked to reflect about their views and expectations concerning their future habitat by means of a conceptual map made up of images which conveyed certain feelings and ideas about the domestic space. They had to choose some images and make a collage which represented their ideal living place. (Figure 3.5)

Activity 2: **IMAGINE your ideal living space**

You will get photographs which convey certain feelings and ideas about domestic space. We will ask to choose some images which altogether represent your ideal living place and describe it in a few sentences.

Figure 3.5. Activity 2. ‘Imagine Your Ideal Living Space’

3.2.3 Evaluation of inputs obtained in the first participatory session

At this point of the process, the task for students was to synthesize and systematize the outcomes obtained during the first participatory session. This process of reflection was carried out from two standpoints: firstly, from the dwellers’ point of view, summarizing their insights on dwelling and housing; and secondly, from the standpoint of architects, describing how the profession could answer dwellers’ demands.

3.2.3.1 Task 4: Reflecting and Communicating

The objective of this task was to start to forge links between the dwellers’ views and needs and

the professional approaches to contemporary housing with the purpose of preparing the next design stage. The material used for this analysis is the information from the participative session: texts, photographs, videos, etc.

Deliverables

The output is an A3 sheet in which every student summarizes, in one topic, the insights of dwellers and reflects on them from an architectural point of view. (Figure 3.6)

Figure 3.6. Deliverable of Task 4

3.2.4 Re-design of the participatory processes: new methods and tools

After analysing the results obtained from the first participatory session (missing information, value of the answers obtained, effectiveness of the communication tools), students had to re-design the communication tool and the participatory methods. As a result of these reflections, two new activities were proposed to be implemented in the next participatory session: Activity 3. 'PLAN your future home, Part 1' and Activity 4. 'PLAN your future home, Part 2', described on the following section.

3.2.5 Implementation of the participatory process: second joint working session

The second participatory session took place on January 14, 2014 (Figure 3.7). The aim of this session was to implement the communication tools that have been redesigned following the experience of the first session.

Figure 3.7. Invitation to the second participatory session

The participatory activities which carried out were:

- **Activity 3.** ‘PLAN your future home, Part 1’. Participants had to name the eight most important activities they perform at home. The activities were placed in concentric circles, with the most important ones located at the centre. Afterwards, they had to draw lines to represent the activities that were related. Finally, they specified if the activities took place within the limits of the household or outside of it (Figure 3.8).

Qué actividades te hacen sentir como en casa?

STEP 0: Every person gets an A4 sheet to write any activities which make them feel like home. If they are ready, they can start the next step.

STEP 1: Now you are asked to choose 8 activities from step 0 and fill them in the gradient.

STEP 2: The next step is to put circular stickers to set in the gradient which personal value you give to each activity, the center means the most value.

STEP 3: We ask you to mark the relations between the activities and comment them on the sheet. For example: playing with the kids after eating is very valuable for me, because...

STEP 4: Please decide now, whether you do the activity inside, outside or in between. With the help of a legend were symbols are given, you can draw next to the circle the symbol for each activity.

Please add all your notes and thoughts with your name on this sheet.

Figure 3.8. Activity 3; ‘Plan Your Future Home, Part 1’

- **Activity 4.** ‘PLAN your future home, Part 2’. Participants selected some of the activities identified in the previous process. Every activity was written in a paper stick. The selected activity was broken down into smaller activities taken place at different times and places. Every activity was written in a paper stick whose size represented the value that the dweller assigned to it. Finally, they had to state if the activities were carried individually, with family members or with the community (Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.9. Activity 4; 'Plan Your Future Home, Part 2'

3.2.6 Creating a design brief based on answers from participants

As the final output of the participatory process, students produced a brief to guide the design of the future dwelling in the building to be refurbished. These guidelines were the result of processing the information that was obtained from the second participatory session. The topics derived from the participants' inputs were analysed by the students. They described the underlying problems and their implications from the social and the architectural points of view.

Task 5: Extracting a Briefing

The objective of this task was to describe an architectural programme and to produce design guidelines, based on the information from the dwellers. This was done by means of a template which contained, on the one hand, the inhabitant's wishes and expectations, on their future dwelling, and on the other hand, some the proposals of the students of architecture to answer those needs. Architectural solutions which responded to the dwellers' demands were described in a verbal and graphic language, understandable to non-professionals (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10. Design guide template

Using this template, students had to provide the following information:

- Dwellers' inputs: These inputs were organized by themes and literally transcribed onto the template.
- The description of the problem: A summary of the themes identified after analysing the inputs from participants.
- The context: Every theme was related to the other analysed themes.
- The architectural response: The student proposed solutions to the issues raised by the dwellers.

Deliverables

An A3 sheet following the template.

3.2.7 Outputs

The list of topics provided by the students, using the previous template was the following:

- **Natural light:** “Natural light, large windows and beautiful views were often mentioned
- **Community:** “Almost all of the participants mentioned that they wish to have an active community and they are willing to share not only rooms but activities”
- **Green housing:** “Many dwellers would like to have green spaces in their houses. Some of them mentioned that sharing a place to plant fruits and vegetables would improve their feeling of living in community and would make them feel better, optimizing natural resources” (Figure 3.11).

Figure 3.11. Design guidelines for “Green Housing”. Students: Alejandro Calleja, Beatriz Ferrao, Izabela Grotowicz, Jeanne Scholtz, Sebastian Baier

- **Child development:** “The dwellers who have children in their families emphasized that it would be important for them to have a special space for their children to play outside their own apartments. This place would have different functions, for example: a place to do drawings and paintings, to play with other kids and to do outdoor

activities”.

- **Productive space:** “Many dwellers mentioned that they are also looking for a space of their own, in their apartments, where they can work or study, do their hobbies or simply relax, listening to some music and reading”.
- **Open kitchen:** “Many people wish a room to share with friends and family for common activities like cooking, eating or just for sitting together” (Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12. Design guidelines for “Open Kitchen”. Students: Alejandro Calleja, Beatriz Ferrao, Izabela Grotowicz, Jeanne Scholtz, Sebastian Baier

- **Relation with the exterior:** “Most of the dwellers socialize in outdoor spaces with their neighbours where they can develop a feeling of community feeling.”
- **Sustainability:** “Consuming organically growth products that contribute to environmental and social sustainability. Re-using of old materials and sharing of goods with the neighbours. Conscious consumption of resources, electricity and water.”
- **Comfort:** “Natural light, large windows with beautiful views. Need for a warm, homely atmosphere. By participating in the design process users can identify with the place of residence, making them feel at home afterwards.”

These A3 sheets were meant to be used for the future inhabitants as a ‘design guide’. That is, as a reference document that would help them to communicate with the architect who would design their dwellings.

3.3 Dissemination activities

The development of the participatory action has been described in the [OIKONET Community Participation](#) blog (Figure 3.13).

Figure 3.13. Community Participation blog

A [presentation](#) summarizing the activities has been posted on the project website and distributed among the network members (Figure 3.14).

Figure 3.14. Summary of the activities distributed on the website

On March 6, 2014, Leandro Madrazo and Angel Martin from the School of Architecture La Salle, presented, through [teleconference](#), the experience of the seminar "Civic Housing", to teachers and students participating in the Ilinden workshop, organized by UKIM, Skopje, Macedonia. OIKONET partners from AF-Belgrade and the Facultad de Arquitectura, Santiago de Chile, were present as well (Figure 3.15).

Figure 3.15. Presentation of the Civic Housing seminar via teleconference.

A [video](#) documenting the work done has been produced and published on the project web portal.

3.4 Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from the experience of designing and implementing the participatory design processes:

- Each participation process is unique: different tools, and methods are required for each particular design process. For this reason, it is difficult to come up with a generic methodology which can be replicated in the different places
- From a pedagogic point of view, a learning space has been created which transcends the limits of the classroom and university
- A shared language (verbal, graphical) is necessary to facilitate the communication between professionals and non-professionals
- The task of the students was to design a communication process to interact with dwellers, more than designing the dwellings themselves. In this way, they could exercise the role of “designers of design processes” rather than of “designers of architectural artefacts”. Therefore, they have been, in fact, developing their skills as mediators and facilitators
- Students acquired a direct knowledge of the housing building and the place –in all of its dimensions. These are the urban, social and the cultural dimensions.
- Citizens developed a feeling of ‘belonging’ with the built environment through their participation on the process
- Through the processes designed and implemented by students and tutors, citizens learned about the knowledge they possessed on the living environment
- Teachers acted as learning designers, creating a blended learning space which integrates the academic and civic activities

The following conclusions are drawn with regard to the participating members of Sostre Civic:

- The participants developed a feeling of ‘belonging’ with their living spaces through their participation on the process
- Through the processes designed and implemented by students and tutors, participants became aware of the knowledge they possessed about the living environment
- As result of this activity, participants felt they were the protagonists of the decision making process of the cooperative

- As result of this activity, participants became more motivated and involved on the cooperative and had a better opinion of it
- Activities such as the ones developed in this participatory action will be integrated on the cooperative regular meetings
- This activity confirmed the importance of bringing together citizens, designers and managers to work together on real projects

4 RIMINI: DEFINING STRATEGIES TO FACILITATE ACCESS TO SOCIAL HOUSING

4.1 Introduction

A participatory action was carried out by Heriscape Association and the Chamber of Architects of Rimini (*Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini*) from June 2014 to March 2015. The activities took place in Rimini, most of them hosted in the premises of the Strategic Plan of Rimini, who collaborated with Heriscape and the Chamber facilitating connections with the members of Rimini society participating in the activities.

The main purpose of the participatory action in Rimini was to define possible and feasible strategies to support solutions for the social housing problems in a medium-size city, fostering the collaboration of the private and public sectors in the proposals and developments of these solutions.

4.2 Description of Rimini housing context

This chapter describes the context of Rimini, starting from the Italian one, studied analysed by the two researchers commissioned by the Chamber of Architects. This first phase enabled to assess the situation of social housing in Rimini, identifying needs, opportunities, demands and supply. The results of the survey of the social housing situation in Rimini were shared in the second stage of the participatory activities with the representatives of Rimini society.

4.2.1 Outlining the Italian context

From the middle of the 1990s, the housing market in Italy has seen a general increase in prices while the income of families has seen a modest increase, generating tension in the market. The traditional public instruments (such as the *Edilizia Residenziale Pubblica (ERP)* – Public Residential housing programme) to assist in such a situation have failed to provide an adequate response.

This phenomenon which started in the larger metropolitan cities has spread to smaller cities like Rimini. The issue of housing has changed over time and become more complex and diversified. In fact, today, the problem of accommodation is not only of interest to the weaker members of society, but also to those increasing numbers of people who even though they have relatively regular and stable incomes, have significant difficulty in accessing the housing market. In summary, the problem of access to housing affects:

- people in emergency housing situations, without the necessary means to live in a safe and dignified space;
- parts of the population in less serious situations that are nevertheless unable to access the housing market because the prices are too high. For such people, the house mortgage or rent significantly affects the normal annual living expenses. Included in this segment are single-income families and single parent families, the young, the elderly and foreigners; in other words, individuals who are extremely different in terms of their needs, available resources and prospects. What they have in common is their difficulty in keeping their homes, whether they are renting or owners.

The tendencies in such circumstances indicate an increase in the difficulty for Italian families to cover house expenses, even if referring to rent levels or to monthly mortgage payments. In 2012, 10% of families surveyed indicated that more than 30% of their income was used for housing costs, the threshold usually considered as a distinction of economic disadvantage.

Compared with 2010, there was a two-percentage point increase in families in this situation.

The phenomenon for those in rented housing is more serious with 37% of income being used for housing costs which increased by 6 percentage points compared to 2010 and 15 percentage points compared to 2002. Although the trend is rising, the impact on homeowners was less acute, 1.2% in 2002 and 2.4% in 2014 (data calculated on all families regardless of whether they had mortgages)¹.

After years of political support for “home ownership”, with an incidence of 70% (the highest in Europe), new needs for flexibility, increasing difficulties in accessing mortgages and an ever increasing demand for temporary housing (caused by an increasingly elastic labour market) are generating the emergent necessity to extend the availability of social housing in the rent market.

The field of housing policy is characterised by numerous public and private housing entities operating at different levels with respect to the needs of different target groups. Even if they try to offer options to different people in need of social housing, often, they act without the coordination and cooperation necessary to identify population demands, define roles for each organization and establish a common policy to provide effective answers to the lack of affordable housing.

The fragmentation of social housing policies, tools, projects and instruments, and the lack of collaboration between the public and private bodies dealing with social housing hinder the effectiveness of any action aimed at solving the housing needs of the “new” sectors (i.e. the “grey area”), which includes those in extremely different circumstances but have the same difficulties to afford housing prices of the real estate market.

This has to be added to new themes and challenges directing urban policy choices over recent years: rehabilitation and redevelopment of run-down urban areas, stopping land use and consumption, requiring quality in urban responses and ecologically sustainable solutions, and promoting participation and community building.

The described situation has important consequences: a new awareness, combined with the present economic crisis, demands new policies and innovative instruments. In this context the instrument called “Piano Casa”, a parallel model to the current system of public residential housing promoted by ERP, has been developed to provide a constructive response using economic and financial instruments like property investment funds and ethical funds. The absence of public resources to sustain housing policy has triggered understanding and co-operation between individuals and public institutions, both at national and local levels, able to deliver expert and actionable responses.

4.2.2 Description of the Rimini case study

Based on this assumption, the Rimini participatory action was set up to encourage, foster, promote and define possible strategies to facilitate the realisation of a social housing programme in a medium-size city (on the basis of which Rimini was proposed as a model for a case study) developed through an integrated approach which involved people from the public and private sectors.

After collecting data and information to outline the Italian context, the researchers of Chamber of Architects conducted a preliminary study of social housing in Rimini by analysing different information sources (among them institutional reports). The first “picture” shows the opportunities and synergies that were shared with the involved stakeholders in the participatory process in the second phase of the process, with the objective of verifying and activating shared strategic actions.

¹ Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, “Social Housing – Il mercato immobiliare in Italia: focus sull’edilizia sociale, Report Monografico 03 – 2014”

Rimini Housing context: needs and opportunities

The situation of the housing market in Rimini is no different to the general situation in Italy.

The high rigidity, scarce liquidity in the rented segment, together with the incapacity of supply and demand to find a common ground have accentuated housing difficulties². With regards to the available housing stock, we see the presence of significant urban assets which are unused or used “unofficially” for rent and the potential availability of new accommodation derives from the transformation and redevelopment of existing housing. What is significant, if confirmed, is there would be 15,000 vacant housing units in the private market in Rimini, and if not adequately dealt with, will probably become areas of urban decline³.

Parallel to the difficult economic situation, Rimini has been facing steadily increasing demographic changes over recent years: a positive trend but unusual compared to other similar situations and contexts in Italy³.

The touristic sector is playing a leading and supporting role for the city; even if it is slowing down; it has maintained its importance over recent years. It is a positive presence in the sense that it crosses and clashes with the housing market dramatically influencing rents and house prices.

Emergency Housing

The current housing market situation in Rimini, together with the emergency housing situation is very peculiar.

To respond to the private rental market average rents of €500 per month for studio apartments, the public housing policies offer €70 per month for a room (affordable housing) and €250-€450 a month for a house with controlled rent⁴.

The demand for affordable housing has grown exponentially over the last 3 years from 900 to 1,600 requests annually, for public assets of 1,600 units of accommodation and which has a turnover of only 3%.

This situation is further compounded by the regional criteria of allocation and stay: the limit of the income to stay in the affordable housing is €51.000 for two years in a row. This limit is really high and could include people who could apply for houses with controlled rent or in the real estate market, and prevents the allocation to those who are really in need⁴⁻⁵.

From the report of the Ministry of Interior released in 2013, the province of Rimini had the highest eviction rate in Italy, one in every 154 households, against an Italian average of one in every 353 in 2013; and in the first months in 2014 there was a further surge.

The data also shows that the evictions for termination represent almost 10% of the total. As already seen, the number of vacant private homes is high: many landlords in the private sector prefer to rent their properties to tourists on short-term lets in order to counter the problem of rent arrears of long-term contracts, considering it to be a safer form of remuneration.

The situation in Rimini can be simplified as it follows: empty houses, citizens requesting rent controlled accommodation and citizens living in affordable housing, but who could afford to access the real estate market.

² Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, “Social Housing – Il mercato immobiliare in Italia: focus sull’edilizia sociale, Report Monografico 03 – 2014”

³ Interview to Arch. Alberto Fattori, Urban Planning Department, Municipality of Rimini

⁴ Interview to Gloria Lisi, Deputy Mayor, Social policies department, Municipality of Rimini

⁵ Interview to Dr Carlo Alberto Celli, vice president of ACER Rimini

Tourism and University

As previously mentioned, the tourism sector supports the economy of the area influencing housing market trends and housing policies.

Data from 2010 shows the continued strength of the sector despite the economic crisis. In addition, the city is regaining its international position thanks to the promotion of its cultural identity and to the presence of the university. There are more than 6.000 students at the university campus in Rimini of whom more than 50% are from outside Rimini and out of these, 65% are applicants from outside the province of Rimini. A remarkable number which the university is looking to cater for by finding the necessary dedicated accommodation.

The “University citadel” already represents a landmark in the heart of the city. The old separation between students and local community has been overcome thanks to the activities developed by students’ associations in the area, involving administrative institutions and citizens.

The university is fully committed to the local cultural development and will play a bigger role in the economic and social context of Rimini in the future⁶.

The third sector

The third sector plays an important role: the associations, organisations, entities belonging to the third sector manage and design numerous projects and programmes to help and reintegrate those people considered to be on the edge of society. In 2011 in Rimini there were almost 130 voluntary organisations operating in the health and social sectors, working on social integration, training and environment⁶.

The housing problem in Rimini is also dealt with in the annual report, "Report on Poverty", drawn up by Caritas, and backed up with references from municipal data, which provides an overview of the social situation of those living on the margins in the city of Rimini.

In 2013, the Social help support desk of Rimini (*Sportello Sociale*) met with 1,452 people and carried out 2,469 interventions. Most of the families encountered had an average of two minors and few families with elderly relatives living at home.

In 2013, as the rate of unemployment increased, so did the number of men who asked the social help support desk for help, while women still managed to find temporary work especially in hotels during the summer period.

Foreign families have much more difficulty in finding housing after being evicted than Italian families, since Italian families, especially those traditionally from Rimini, often have a network of friends and family who can somehow provide support.

Caritas underlines that, due to the worsening of the economic crisis, more and more people have started to request their primary care services, in addition to the homeless: people having a house but cannot afford to pay the rent, bills and sometimes mortgage. It is therefore a very complex and difficult period for these new users of Caritas, people who would never have thought of being in a position of need, among them many families with children. According to Caritas, there would be more evictions, even for those who live in public housing. There is also a growing number of people who live in holiday apartments during the winter and are unable to find affordable accommodation during the summer when prices rise significantly.

At the same time, the number of people living on the streets has increased; they find shelter in abandoned houses or shacks, or build shelters with waste materials under bridges, in parks or on the beach. They even choose not to sleep at Caritas for fear of losing what they consider to

⁶ Rimini Municipality, L'Arengo, Magazine of Rimini Municipality, March 2011

be their 'lucky homes' on the streets. According to Caritas, the situation is becoming ever more serious⁷.

4.3 The participatory process: approach and activities

4.3.1 Objectives of the action

As underlined by the description of the context, due to different causes, housing demand in Rimini has been transformed, becoming more complex and diversified, and increased in number. It is characterized by the presence of “atypical” housing demand: strong increase in single households, single-parent families, immigrants, temporary workers, off-campus students and others.

Sustained by this new “atypical” demand, the extension of the housing emergency is affecting intermediate segments of the population (“grey area”) who until recently were untouched by such difficulties.

This part of population is unable to meet its housing needs on the open market for economic reasons or due to a lack of appropriate options on the supply side.

The goal of social housing is to improve the conditions of these people by favouring the creation of dignified social and living conditions so that they may not only have access to suitable dwellings, but also to rich and meaningful human relations.

What is clear is that the fragmentation of social housing policies, tools, projects and instruments, and the lack of collaboration between the public and private bodies dealing with social housing hinder the effectiveness of any action defined to provide an answer to the housing needs of the “new” sectors (“grey area”) together with most disadvantaged sectors of the population.

In light of the lack of public resources to sustain a social housing policy, the co-operation between individuals, associations, private bodies and institutions becomes necessary.

For this reason, Heriscape and Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini proposed the creation of a participatory action in Rimini, involving different partners and institutions to set up some criteria to overcome the difficulties of the social housing sector. Having a participatory approach will help to reach different aims:

- To create a permanent round table (possibly evolving into a Steering Committee) involving local associations and institutions committed to facilitate access to housing and to assure the welfare of the population;
- To identify social housing problems and opportunities, to set a baseline for future actions and policies;
- To outline possible solutions and pilot actions carried out with the participation of the involved stakeholders;
- To come up with a methodological approach which contributes to establishing a broader housing policy at the local and national levels;
- To disseminate the outcomes of this action at the national and international level, and to evaluate their possible application to different European contexts. By defining needs and opportunities, the aim is to set some criteria for future actions and policies that have to be developed by the participants. The proposed actions will foster the collaboration among the partners in order to effectively respond to the request for social housing

⁷ Caritas Diocesana, Report delle povertà, Rimini, 2013

coming from different sectors of the population.

In the next chapter the different stages of the implementation of the participatory action will be described: starting from the first time the stakeholders met, going through the interviews and ending with the two round tables.

4.3.2 Kick-off: first meeting in Rimini and interviews with stakeholders

From the very beginning of designing the participatory action in Rimini, Heriscape and Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini took the opportunity to invite the “potential” stakeholders of the Rimini action to the second work group 3 meeting of OIKONET.

The institutions, organizations and associations invited to participate to Rimini action, explained their role and provided examples of good practices. It was a fundamental step for the action because it demonstrated their will to work on the action, hoping to create the base of future collaboration among the actors.

After the meeting of WP3, from June to October 2014, two researchers from Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini worked on the description of Rimini housing context (part of the previous chapters). At the beginning their activity was developed analysing different information sources, afterwards through interviews with the participants that are important local promoters in the housing sector.

Interviews with stakeholders were carried out in the period between November and December 2015 (Figure 4.1). The purpose of the interviews was to get in touch with the context of Rimini and learn approaches, working methods and activities carried out by the stakeholders on issues related to social housing. All subjects were given a questionnaire with the questions which would be asked during the interview.

Figure 4.1. Interviews

The information collected from each subject, was useful to structure and formulate actionable proposals. The questionnaire can be summarized in the following points.

- Description of the subject (role and organization);
- Description of the activities performed by the subject related to the theme of housing;

- Perceptions of social housing them in Rimini in terms of weaknesses, opportunities, specificities;
- Analysis of the relationships existing between the various entities.

The subjects involved and interviewed were 10 and can be grouped into the following categories:

- Political institutions: Municipality of Rimini (Housing Policies Department, Youth Policy Department, Urban Planning and Territorial Management Department);
- Institutional bodies: ACER Rimini (Emilia Romagna Affordable Housing Agency);
- Economic entities: Carim Foundation (Bank Foundation);
- Entities belonging to the third sector: Papa Giovanni XXIII Association, San Giuseppe Foundation, Slash Association, Caritas, Fratelli è Possibile Social Cooperative.

The interviews also enable the architects to write a brief description of each participant:

Housing Policy Department – Rimini Municipality

Municipal Department that manages the promotion and development of projects related to housing policies, as part of social policies, which are aimed at a different target groups.

It works closely with the third sector on many projects. Good examples resulting from this collaboration in recent years are the *Housing First* and *Hotel Association* projects.

Youth Policies Department – Rimini Municipality

Municipal Department which deals with the promotion and management of proposals and measures for young people aged 16 to 32 years. The main activity of this unit is to offer space and facilities for the creation of youth centres.

Compared to the housing policy unit, this unit seeks to promote initiatives aimed at different young people (students, young workers, young couples, etc.).

Urban Planning and Territorial Management Department – Rimini Municipality

Municipal Department engaged in the planning and management of planning instruments. The department has recently been looking at repositioning planning policies, directing them towards redevelopment and no longer towards land use.

ACER

Azienda Casa Emilia-Romagna

ACER Rimini:

Economic and autonomous public body in charge of managing public housing, following aspects of development and management for Rimini.

Currently ACER is responsible for the management (140 buildings), construction (2 new construction projects of residential buildings under rent control) and collaboration with the private market. It is also engaged in housing research on behalf of the Municipality, to meet emergency housing needs.

**Fondazione
Cassa di Risparmio
di Rimini**

Carim Bank Foundation

Holding of the Bank Cassa di Risparmio di Rimini; created with the objective of promoting the development and growth of social, economic, cultural and institutional

areas of the territory.

The Foundation takes action in the following areas:

- art
- education
- elder care
- charity work
- voluntary work
- territorial development (social housing lies in this field)

The Carim Foundation joined the estate fund FERSH (Social Housing Fund Emilia Romagna) with the back of the real estate company Polaris. For a complex issue such as housing, the Foundation prefers to rely on qualified assistance to achieve the best results with the funds available.

To date, Polaris has been engaged in a scouting phase (research of areas) on the territory of Rimini. The Carim Foundation has had the role of introducing Polaris to Rimini presenting the various actors (public and private) that deal with housing in Rimini. Among other activities, the Foundation supports financially UNI.Rimini. In the past, together with UNI.Rimini, Carim had created student halls with about 80 beds through the redevelopment of an old unused hotel.

Papa Giovanni XXII Association:

Association working with people excluded from society, the poor and other disadvantaged groups (disabled, drug addicts, homeless, sex workers) to provide care and support.

The association now manages several facilities in the area of Rimini:

- *Family homes:* multi-user facilities for extended reception-shelter. These are family groups of 10/14 people belonging to different age groups and with a multitude of problems.
- *First aid:* first aid facilities and temporary shelter for people in critical situations (drug addicts, the homeless)

Currently, the association is engaged in the *Housing First* project, an experimental project for the reception and rehabilitation of homeless people.

San Giuseppe Foundation:

Foundation dealing with assistance and social equality for orphans, single mothers or young mothers in need.

Over time, the activities of the Foundation have changed and evolved giving assistance to people with other disadvantages.

As a refuge centre, the foundation has changed from an institute to apartments: small communities that have replaced the original family unit and are accompanied by professional educators.

Today the foundation is committed to the social housing project *Tre Tende* (Three tents).

Slash Association:

The Students Association of the University Campus of Rimini was created to provide a response to the students' needs and to be the bridge between the university and the territory, two realities that so far have remained distant. In 2013, participating in the European project "Youth Adrinet" in collaboration with Rimini Municipality, together with other issues and themes concerning students, the association complains about the lack of student housing from the private rental market. Within

this programme, they designed a proposal called *Housing Esperienziale* (Experiential Housing), a project of social housing for students thought up entirely by the students of Slash.

Caritas Rimini:

Caritas is the Pastoral Body of the *CEI* (Italian Episcopal Conference) which promotes charity. Caritas provides services to help the needy and the poor in the territory of Rimini, through a voluntary association and a social cooperative. The social cooperative, *Madonna della Carità*, manages first and second reception centres for people in need. The first reception centre provides an emergency service and temporary shelter, the second reception centre provides reintegration pathways of 3, 6 or 12 months.

At the moment the cooperative is heavily engaged in the project *S.P.R.A.R* (*Sistema di Protezione per Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati* - Protection system for refugees and immigrants) for the reception of immigrants and refugees. Today Caritas houses 30 migrants in two buildings run by support workers (in collaboration with *San Giuseppe Foundation*), carrying out a programme of integration.

The houses are big (200 and 500 square meters) and isolated to have less impact on the territory. Furthermore, the Cooperative is involved in the *Mare Nostrum* project and hosts 50 refugees. Caritas participates as a partner to the *Housing First* project, mentioned previously.

Caritas was a partner of the *San Giuseppe Fondazione* for the *Tre Tende* project: after the realization of the project, Caritas would have carried out the management, but due to economic problems it pulled out of this project.

Caritas has a clear view on emergency housing, investing many resources in needs analysis: its observations on poverty two years ago resulted in the publication of a report concerning housing.

Social Cooperative Fratelli è Possibile:

Cooperative dealing, among other things, with conflict mediation. It is engaged in various projects and initiatives of mediation and social management and regularly collaborates with the Rimini Municipality, Acer and Caritas. It is currently working on the *Tre Tende* and *Housing First* projects.

4.3.2.1 Synthesis and Analysis of input obtained from the interviews

The material collected during the interviews enabled the researchers together with Heriscape to create a framework of the housing situation in Rimini and to map the entities involved in it.

The city can be seen as a very active society in which the city administration, attentive to housing issues, has put implemented a number of effective welfare policies. The extensive and active network of third sector associations ensures targeted interventions in the area to solve specific problems (care of the elderly, the disabled, drug addicts, orphans, the homeless).

Unfortunately, the lack of economic resources, in line with the national situation, slows the process and makes it difficult to develop and realize complex projects.

By analysing the interviews and the data collected, the researchers identified four projects proposed or under development that are distinguished by their innovative character and

adherence to the specificities of the territory of Rimini.

The four projects or proposal (*Housing First*, *Housing Esperienziale*, *Tre Tende* and the social housing foundation FERSH) were analysed in order to identify the gaps and opportunities to be presented during the participatory meeting, underling critical and weak aspects.

The selected proposals are illustrative examples of the housing situation in Rimini to work on together with the participants: they are addressed to different target groups, proposed by different entities (private, public or third sector), and show critical points and aspects, but also good practices that could be discussed in the round tables planned for the action.

The researchers from the Chamber, with the coordination of Heriscape, summarized the four selected projects, output of the first phase and useful tool to open the debate with the participants in the activities. For each project they identified the main aim, the target group, the promoters, the project type, the funding typologies, and a brief description of the contents, weaknesses and opportunities.

Following the detailed analysis and description of each selected proposals:

1. *Housing First*

Goal:

Social reintegration of homeless people

Target group:

Homeless people with serious psychiatric problems and poor health aggravated by a lengthy period of time on the streets

Promoters:

Papa Giovanni XXIII association, with the collaboration of Caritas, Cooperativa Eucrante Cooperative and Fratelli è Possibile Cooperative

Project Type:

Supply of housing, available apartments in existing buildings to pave the way for social reintegration.

Funding system:

Public fund: The municipality allocates funds to pay the rent for apartments, or to act as guarantor for tenants in cases where tenants can cover part of housing costs and expenses.

Situation in December 2014:

Research of dwellings. They have to be found in the real estate market: it means finding private owners willing to participate to the project.

Brief description of the project:

The *Housing First* project acknowledges the house as the primary role in the reintegration path of homeless people. The house is conceived as a tool of empowerment, and commitment: the hosted person, among other things, gets an apartment, which in turn allows him to access the health and social services he needs.

The apartments have to be found in the real estate market. The associations responsible

to find them are trying to come to an agreement on rents with the owners, negotiating on studio apartments of 30-35 square meters. According to the original project the people hosted should pay a percentage of the housing costs that may be around 50% or 30% of the cost of renting and utilities, if this is not possible the municipality of Rimini has allocated funds to cover any arrears or to cover all the costs for one year.

Weaknesses / opportunities:

The dwellings search is a delicate phase: the houses must be found in a welcoming and friendly environment for the participants of the programme, without running the risk of segregation. It will be essential to create a network of relationships in the neighbourhood that can help the homeless to regain independence. It is important to underline that the success of this project depends on the effective support and initiatives for social reintegration.

2. *Housing Esperienziale:*

Goal:

Recover and convert a hotel into student housing, keeping an area for tourist accommodation.

Target group:

Students

Promoters:

Slash association

Project proposal:

Recovery of existing hotel structure to create student housing with potential work opportunities for young people

Funding system:

None.

Situation in December 2014:

The proposal stopped. The Slash started mapping possible buildings that could be converted.

Brief description of the project proposal:

The idea is to recover and reuse disused or abandoned hotels to provide bed spaces and gathering places at reduced rents for students. A part of the business plan might also include the provision of meals for the homeless.

Weaknesses/opportunities

The idea of the project is still at an embryonic stage, and at this stage it is difficult to identify possible forms of financing and collaboration with other partners, without a precise definition of goals, strategies, needs, etc. It has yet to be figured out whether the planning instrument now in force allows the transformation, albeit temporarily, of hotels into collective living facilities and housing. Despite these problems, the project is highly innovative and specific as it addresses the theme of decommissioned hotels in

a new way.

3. *Tre Tende Project:*

Goal:

Answer to diverse and multiple needs connected to the theme of housing. The project idea was conceived to implement a real housing intervention with social integration, with respect to four basic principles:

- designing quality housing;
- ensuring environmental sustainability and energy efficiency;
- offering services to promote social inclusion;
- containment of rents.

Target groups:

Adults with moderate to severe disabilities, young-adults with experiences "outside the family", unaccompanied migrant youth, family and people socially and economically marginalized, people staying temporarily in the area.

Promoters:

The social housing project *Villaggio Tre Tende* (Three Tents Village) is the result of collaboration and partnership between local authorities, private investors and the some institutions of the third sector from Rimini. Sponsored by the San Giuseppe Foundation together with social cooperatives Madonna della Carità (Caritas), L'Aquilone and Fratelli è Possibile.

Project Type:

Social housing: new constructions providing units with controlled rents together with social intervention and accompanying services, to develop ways for individuals to mature and grow socially.

Funding system:

The involved partners directly invest their economic, human and social resources. The resources used by each entity in the first phase are intended for the architectural construction of the village and the activation of all the activities and services provided by the project.

In the later stages, the partners will be directly responsible for further investment or procurement of the resources required for the maintenance and further development of the village.

The project expects all the various stakeholders and promoters to be present in the village, with attention to specific areas of administration. Specifically, different areas related to sustainability are distinguished such as:

- economic sustainability;
- social sustainability;
- organizational-managerial sustainability;
- energy sustainability.

Situation in December 2014:

The project was presented to the Municipality and the partners were expecting to get the approval in December 2014. Thereafter they have a medium-term objective of "networking" with other institutions to find economic/financial solutions.

Brief description of the project:

Three new buildings are designed to be constructed alongside the existing Casa Bronzetti on land owned by the San Giuseppe Foundation, in Rimini (area donated by the family Bronzetti).

Recipients are then offered equipped housing facilities suited to their specific needs, in a socially integrated environment.

To this end, the various project partners will provide the following services:

- housing assistance;
- personalized courses aimed at becoming independent and increasing personal and social skills;
- parenting support;
- families are going to be followed in the process of social integration;
- educational activities and workshops;
- social and conflict mediation;
- recreational activities.

The permanent presence of the social mediation service will act as a social element of cohesion between the different situations in the Village and the proposed activities, in order to develop a social and supportive network.

Weaknesses/ opportunities:

The project, as a result of collaboration between the third sector is deeply rooted in the territory and has a great deal of experience. The proposal of social management is a strong innovative idea.

The proposed economic and financial sustainability is too weak to support charitable work and the project in its current state appears to be unable to find financial partners willing to invest. Specifically referring to the project, it is important to underline that the staying should be temporary, usually this limit is not respected. The partners involved have to be responsible of the effectiveness of this aspect.

4. FERSH - Fondo Emilia Romagna Social Housing**Goal:**

Increased financing for social housing as defined in the Ministerial Decree of 22 April 2008, in the region Emilia Romagna, activating offers of housing with significantly lower rents compared to the market, with widely varying levels for each intervention according to sustainability, housing context, technical characteristics and social services provided (support, integration etc.).

Target groups:

Not only young couples and single-income families, but also new social groups with specific needs such as students, immigrants, commuters, people with temporary

employment contracts and the elderly.

Promoters:

It was created by some banking foundations of Emilia Romagna-including Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Rimini (*Carim Bank Foundation of Rimini*), in close cooperation with the Region Emilia Romagna, through the creation of a specific fund managed by the company's asset management division Polaris.

Project Type:

Social housing projects that could be developed in newly constructed buildings or the rehabilitation of existing ones, integrating actions and services.

Funding system:

It is based on the IMS (Integrated System of Real Estate Funds) on two levels:

- Regional housing funds and / or local authorities involved in the promotion and implementation of private social housing interventions (Fondazione CARIM)
- a National Fund, the Investment for Living Fund, run by CDPI Sgr (FIA), which invests in minority stakes of up to 40% in local funds.

Fund management combines social content and profitability targets, the latter set so as to be of interest to potential institutional investors who support the activities of the Fund.

Situation in December 2014:

Polaris Sgr, through the mediation of *CARIM* Bank Foundation, is scouting areas and projects in Rimini looking for possible development actions.

Brief description of the project:

The intervention must be structured on several levels: urban, social and financial.

Interventions should be placed in areas with strong housing potential, which are well-connected by public transport services and have commercial and public services (schools, hospitals, green areas and recreational facilities etc.).

Interventions should be made in a variety of building types and parts of housing to meet the needs of different groups of users and encourage the formation of adequate mix housing. The interventions encompass social planning and support to facilitate the inclusion of the disadvantaged (e.g. social and health support, support in finding a job and so on.)

The buildings should conform to the principles of environmental sustainability and energy saving, using wherever possible, sources of alternative energy.

Initiatives must be sustainable from the point of view of economic and financial aspects: the package of intervention should be robust, financed by the banks, and with an aggregate performance in line with the objectives of the Fund. Typically, each intervention should bring at least 100 units of housing or have a total value of at least 10 million euros.

Weaknesses / opportunities:

The Fund is now presented as well-established and functioning, guaranteed by a high level of professionalism in the management of all phases of intervention by the financial and social entities contributing to the realization of projects.

It will be interesting to evaluate the opportunity of opening the social management to the third sector which is more rooted in the territory.

The economic-financial sustainability of the initiative requires a series of parameters

and investment criteria to ensure an accurate, but at the same time slow, selection of project areas.

4.3.2.2 Deliverables: stakeholders profile and project files

As foreseen by the work plan of Rimini participatory action, the content of interviews was collected in a video made during the interviews.

At the conclusion of this phase two outcomes had been completed by the Chamber of Architects with support from Heriscape and agreed with stakeholders: the profiling of the stakeholders and an A3 file of each proposal selected.

The stakeholders' profiles were delivered to the participants as a reference tool. They provide the description of the institution (or association), its mission, its social target, its projects on-going) and it was and still is useful to share information and knowledge but also to define common actions to develop.

The proposals were documented and prepared to be presented to the stakeholders in the round tables to start the discussion and the debate in order to define possible criteria for the initiatives and to overcome the difficulties and critical aspects of each project (Figure 4.2).

1. HOUSING FIRST

obiettivo:

reinserimento di persone senza fissa dimora

target di riferimento:

persone senza fissa dimora con gravi problemi psichiatrici, sanitari spesso aggravati da una lunga permanenza in strada

soggetti promotori:

Associazione Papa Giovanni XXIII, Caritas, Cooperativa Eurante e Cooperativa Fratelli è Possibile

tipologia d'intervento:

offerta di alloggi, disponibili su patrimonio edilizio esistente per la creazione di un percorso di assistenza e reinserimento sociale di persone senza fissa dimora

tipologia di finanziamento:

finanziamento pubblico

Il comune stanziava dei fondi per pagare gli affitti degli appartamenti o per fare da garante con i locatari nel momento in cui la persona ospitata fosse in grado di partecipare a parte delle spese.

stato dell'arte:

ricerca degli appartamenti

breve descrizione del progetto:

La casa come strumento di responsabilizzazione

Gli alloggi sono reperiti sul libero mercato e si sta cercando di trovare accordi per canoni calmierati, si tratta di **monolocali di 30-35 mq**. Secondo il progetto originario la persona ospitata dovrebbe partecipare per una percentuale che può aggirarsi intorno al 50% o 30% alle spese di locazione e utenza, nel caso questo non avvenga il Comune di Rimini ha stanziato dei fondi per coprire le eventuali morosità o farsi carico della spesa totale.

carenze / opportunità:

la ricerca degli appartamenti è una fase delicata poiché questi devono essere reperiti in un **contesto accogliente** e ben disposto verso le persone interessate dal programma per non correre il rischio di fenomeni di segregazione.

Sarà fondamentale creare una **rete di rapporti stimolanti** nel quartiere che possano aiutare i senza tetto a recuperare autonomia.

Per la riuscita di questo progetto sembra fondamentale **la fase di accompagnamento**.

- Trovare appartamenti a buon mercato o accordi con proprietari per canoni concordati;
- Costruire una rete di rapporti stimolanti nel quartiere;
- Trovare quartieri e condomini accoglienti;

Domande:

- Quanto tempo dura la copertura da parte del Comune?
- Si sta pensando a forme contrattuali particolari per gli affitti?

Figure 4.2. Example of a documented proposal

4.3.3 Round Table 1

Further activities were planned to foster the participation and collaboration of institutions, associations, and private bodies dealing with housing and to foment the development of participatory action in Rimini.

With this purpose, in the second stage of the action two round tables were organised to discuss possible solutions to be carried out by the participants involved (Figure 4.3).

The planned meetings were designed to help the representatives of the Rimini community to come up with strategies to find common links and then work together on the four selected projects and proposals analysed by the researchers.

OIKONET
A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning
www.oikonet.org

SOCIAL HOUSING IN RIMINI: NEEDS AND OPPORTUNITIES
Rimini, Sede del Piano Strategico | Piazzale Fellini, 3 | 19 febbraio 2015 ore 14.30

Invito al TAVOLO DI LAVORO sul Social Housing

L'Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini e l'associazione Heriscape in collaborazione con il Piano Strategico di Rimini, organizzano il primo dei due tavoli di lavoro partecipati sul Social Housing, nell'ambito del progetto europeo OIKONET.

Il primo tavolo si terrà a Rimini a Rimini lunedì 19 febbraio 2015 dalle ore 14.30 alle ore 17.30. L'incontro di lavoro è dedicato alla possibilità di elaborare proposte sul tema dei bisogni e delle opportunità di finanziamento e investimento nell'housing sociale nel territorio riminese.

Soggetti invitati
Comune di Rimini | Politiche sociali,
Politiche giovanili, Settore pianificazione
ACER Rimini
Associazione Slash
Caritas
Fondazione CARIM Rimini
Fondazione Papa Giovanni XXIII
Fondazione San Giuseppe
Cooperativa Fratelli è Possibile
UNI.Rimini

Si prega di confermare la partecipazione al tavolo.

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Lifelong Learning Programme

Figure 4.3. Invitation to the first round table

4.3.3.1 Description of the activities

The first round table meeting was held in Rimini, in the premises of Rimini Strategic Plan, on February 19, 2015 (Figure 4.4). It was coordinated by Simona Rotteglia of Heriscape, and Pietro Cesari and Giacomo Quercia from the Chamber of Architects.

It was attended by the following entities: Municipality of Rimini (Youth Policies Department, Urban Planning and Territorial Management Department), Acer Rimini, Carim Bank Foundation, Papa Giovanni XXIII Association, San Giuseppe Foundation, Slash Association, Caritas and Fratelli è Possibile Social Cooperative. Also participating in the discussions were some advisers of the Chamber of Architects of Rimini with his president Roberto Ricci.

The discussions focused on the four selected projects with the aim of finding synergies and joint strategies among the various stakeholders in the development of projects.

Mediators delivered the descriptions of the projects so that the participants could use them as a tool for development and to support the debate by: sharpening proposals, highlighting elements for discussion, suggesting solutions to critical issues or identifying opportunities for collaboration.

After the introduction by Simona Rotteglia who summarized the objectives of the OIKONET project, detailing those related to the participatory activities in Rimini, Pietro Cesari and Giacomo Quercia presented the analysis of the four projects, highlighting the weaknesses, opportunities and areas to resolve.

After the presentation of each proposal, all the participants took the floor to present their views on the considerations presented, and, if necessary, update the framework provided and stimulate debate.

This was followed by an interesting debate and a comparison between the various stakeholders who generated the first strategic proposals for the resolution of the problems and critical aspects identified for each proposal.

At the end of the meeting the participants were asked to work on the difficulties and opportunities that emerged and to implement the proposals and suggestions collected (for example the possible collaborations), in anticipation of the second round table meeting.

Figure 4.4. First round table

4.3.3.2 Evaluation of output and input obtained during the first round table

The input concerning the four proposals collected during the discussions showed the following general criticisms:

- lack of available economic resources;
- need for greater communication between institutions in the third sector and administration of certain projects (*Housing Esperienzale*);
- need for greater sharing between entities of public administration on certain projects.

In order to deepen the reflections on the specific proposals, different suggestions for every project were expressed by the participants and collected by the coordinator.

Housing First: At the moment of the first round table (two months later considering the interviews), three dwellings among the ten provided by the project have been identified, one of which is already tenanted. The Papa Giovanni association is in charge of identifying the apartments, but also the people who are going to live in them.

The association is facing a difficulty in reaching agreements with the owners for contracts with rent control, even if the Papa Giovanni completely guarantees all the payment thanks to the Administration funds provided for the realization for the project.

The network of the association helped to find apartments only by word of mouth, but this is not sufficient. One of the participants of the roundtable, from Acer, expressed their willingness to

help the Papa Giovanni XIII association find other dwellings: Acer Rimini has information on private owners in the city who would potentially be available to participate to a project with the conditions they offer.

Villaggio Tre Tende: At the moment of the first round table, the project is in the withdrawal phase of the building permit. Major problems related to financing remain. Thanks to the participatory round table of OIKONET, the San Giuseppe Foundation consulted the *Carim* Bank Foundation about a possible agreement with *Polaris sgr* to investigate the possibility of including Three Tents Project in the one financed by the Bank Foundation.

Housing Esperienziale: the proposal attracted a lot of interest during the first round table from many participants because of its innovation and specific characteristics. However, the idea was still at an embryonic stage and this means that there are still doubts related to proposal details concerning need of the students, best location, management, planning regulations and possible funding sources. Anyway, during the debate, the Slash Students association manage to receive a lot of useful information and contacts to start shaping the proposals. All the suggestions should be considered as potential successful initiatives, but the first steps must be to design and develop the proposals, by creating the appropriate networks and by involving other participants in the action.

FERSH Fund (Emilia Romagna Social Housing Fund): The fund was called into question several times during the discussions. However, it seems that the parameters and criteria of *Polaris* cannot meet the needs of the various projects presented at the meeting.

The round table was an interesting and operational tool, through which it was possible to share problems, experiences and know-how, and useful for the development of the projects fielded.

4.3.3.3 Deliverables

Heriscape wrote a minute of the first round table which was shared with the participants. The written report of the meeting collected all the input, conclusions and information fundamental to start working on the proposals. The day was recorded to become part of the video of Rimini action. Furthermore, at the end of the meeting, the participants were interviewed to collect and gather their evaluations and considerations at the conclusion of the first round table meeting.

The researchers from the Architect Board of Rimini summarized the results of the first round table in a presentation. Heriscape and the Architect Board also wrote a report defining some guidelines and a simplified methodology for the proposal *Housing esperenziale* to be shared with Slash association as a tool to develop and better implement the proposal to respond to student housing needs in Rimini.

4.3.4 Round Table 2

Figure 4.5. Second round table

Besides being an interesting space for debate, the first participatory round table opened some small glimmers of hope for possible synergies, collaborations and interactions among the participants.

The work group of Heriscape and Architect Board, for the second round table (Figure 4.5), systematically organised all the suggestions and applications collected in order to receive a precise picture of all the participants and “recorded proof”, which is fundamental to implementing a framework of collaboration and exchange among the representatives of Rimini community involved in actions to promote social housing projects, as well as to strengthen their positions and roles.

Some of the participants were requested to expand on specific aspects concerning the four proposals, supposed to be explained in the second round table.

Finally, one important aim was brought to the table: the possibility of the round table of OIKONET action to evolve into a permanent Steering Committee on Social Housing in Rimini.

4.3.4.1 Description of the activities

The second round table meeting was held in Rimini on March 13 2015, in the premises of Rimini Strategic Plan.

It was coordinated by Simona Rotteglia and Filippo Boschi of Heriscape, Pietro Cesari and Giacomo Quercia of Rimini Architects Board (Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini) and was attended by the following entities: *Municipality of Rimini (Policies housing department)*, *ACER Rimini*, *Papa Giovanni XXIII Association*, *San Giuseppe Foundation*, *Slash Association*, *the Agency for the Strategic Plan of Rimini*.

Simona Rotteglia introduced the round table. Pietro Cesari and Giacomo Quercia presented a summary of the deliberations made on the four projects, reporting suggestions, point of views and interventions by the participants in the first round table.

In the second round table only two of the four proposals were considered: *Housing Esperienzale* and *Villaggio Tre Tende* project.

The project *Housing Esperienzale* was proposed by Slash Association in response to the lack of student accommodation to converting an unused hotel into a mixed use building: housing both student and tourist accommodation.

PROPOSTA PER UN METODO DI SVILUPPO DEL PROGETTO HOUSING ESPERIENZIALE

Step 1- Proposta dettagliata:

- numero di camere richieste in base alla domanda degli studenti;
- indicare aree più congeniali per alloggiare gli studenti e rendere chiari i criteri di scelta (vicinanza facoltà, parcheggi, zone pedonali...)

Confronto:

- confrontarsi con l'amministrazione (direzione pianificazione) su questi punti per verificare esistenza di criticità urbanistiche. L'amministrazione può essere utile per aiutare a definire le condizioni entro cui sarà possibile convertire alberghi in residenze.

Risultato:

scelta dell'area o delle aree e dei criteri urbanistici

Step 2- Mappatura:

- mappatura degli immobili disponibili (in quanto già fuori mercato o marginali) e valutazioni in base alla capienza, stato di manutenzione, incidenza dei lavori necessari per la conversione.

Confronto:

- aprire un dialogo con gli albergatori. Essere in grado di illustrare la proposta e i vantaggi che si potrebbe trarre dall'operazione.

Risultato:

individuazione dell'immobile o dei possibili immobili

Step 3- Fattibilità economica e gestione:

- business plan

Confronto:

- aprire un confronto con Unirimini e Unibo per verificare la possibilità di stendere accordi per realizzare studentati.
- lavorare in stretto contatto con Politiche Giovanili al fine di individuare possibili elementi di agevolazione.
- ricerca di partner « industriale » per la gestione (a meno che non credano di possedere tutte le expertise)
- ricerca di partner finanziari (Polaris, istituti di credito, bandi ecc...).

Risultato:

definire le condizioni operative per l'attuazione.

Figure 4.6. Fact sheet delivered to participants

The participants were given the analysis sheet on the project which illustrated a possible programme of action to be taken, to make the idea more concrete and competitive, with the idea of seeking potential funding (Figure 4.6).

The discussion helped the students to understand a possibly methodology, but at the same time, by meeting in the round table, they established some potential connections with other community stakeholders, who could offer their experience, knowledge and work with them to develop the proposal.

The *Villaggio Tre Tende* project was promoted by San Giuseppe Foundation which managed to create a working group to overcome the critical points the project was facing. San Giuseppe Foundation, Rimini Municipality, ACER Rimini with the mediation and coordination of the Strategic Plan of Rimini, planned another meeting immediately after the second round table focused to continue working on this project.

At the end of the meeting the possibility of creating a permanent Steering Committee on Social Housing in Rimini, starting with the participants of OIKONET action, was proposed and discussed. The participants agreed that one entity should become the reference point for all the other members and defined the general aims and objectives of the committee to be effective in the development of projects.

4.3.4.2 Evaluation of output and input obtained during the second round table meeting

From the second round table it was possible to confirm some observations already made at the end of the first meeting.

It was observed that many initiatives suffered economic problems: public resources and the spending power of the administration are very limited and often the third sector does not have funds to develop projects.

The discussions also highlighted the difficulty in taking action in contexts such as a small-medium size city like Rimini, where the firms active nowadays are only interested in large scale investments for which they need large spaces which are not usually available in small-medium size cities.

Finally, it was clear that there is a lack of knowledge of the different needs of social housing. Many organisations operating in the area are strongly connected to the welfare sector, which means that often the individuals they cater for are not part of the "grey area". Therefore, filling this gap is another good reason to create a Steering Committee on Social Housing in Rimini. The Committee will involve everyone in the supply chain and will be a place to exchange experiences, knowledge and know-how. In this way, over time, it will actively monitor the issue and try to provide effective responses and optimize available resources.

The participants of the round table meeting were requested to consider the problems and better define the need for housing, to evaluate the possibility of transforming the proposals made in the working group into opportunities, and to express the willingness to foster a continuous dialogue between the parties as a key basis for future actions developed by the participants.

4.3.4.3 Deliverables

Heriscape wrote the minutes of the second round table which was shared with the participants. The day was recorded to become part of the video of Rimini action. Furthermore, at the end of the meeting, the participants were interviewed to collect and gather their evaluations and considerations at the conclusion of the first round table meeting.

The conclusions of the second round table were summarised as part of an illustrative brochure, describing the activities.

4.4 Verification and sharing of conclusions and outcomes.

4.4.1 Analysis and critical investigation of the results of Rimini participatory action

As expected, the participatory action in Rimini gave those present the chance to discuss possible solutions and actions to be carried out by the stakeholders involved.

The following points can be highlighted as a reflection of the whole activity:

- In the area of Rimini there are a large number of agents involved in projects dealing with social housing programmes. However, many of these today are concerned with very specific target groups and often linked to those in critical or emergency situations; very few are concerned with the 'grey area';
- Information about the stakeholders, whether institutional or not, involved in social housing and illustrating positive experiences is fundamental. In this way, it is possible to spread new awareness to address the problems of those in the 'grey area' and to allow local people to relate more positively with stakeholders who wish to invest in the Rimini area. Furthermore, the Rimini municipality often asks for a precise picture reflecting all the sectors represented by the institutions, organisations and associations dealing with housing in Rimini, in order to strengthen the social public policy according to the real need of the city. The round tables helped to go in this direction: the participants sharing their knowledge and experience the participants sharing their knowledge and experience could come up with a methodological approach, which can be considered a contribution to the local housing policy;
- The stakeholders involved in social housing in Italy today often perform real estate transactions at a scale not comparable in magnitude to that of an average city like Rimini. The experience in Rimini shows the need to work on different types of financing, based on the medium-small context.
- By experiencing the discussion in the round tables, the participants understood the importance of creating a network of institutions, associations, private bodies (etc...) to develop, thanks to their integration, effective projects to offer different options of social housing. After the discussion, the stakeholders were convinced that a tight collaboration could help them to successfully apply for funds (e.g. usually private funds require big projects, while the ones proposed from the third sector are too small in terms of quantity and dimension).

Each organization participating in this process is now aware of the activities carried out by other participants: knowing each other help the development of some collaboration and strengthen the chance for some proposals to respond efficiently and effectively to the existing social housing demand. For example, the Project *Tre Tende – Three Tents Village* managed to create a smaller network with some of the participants to try to unblock the situation and speed up the process to realise the intervention.

- The Rimini Social Housing Steering Committee is considered an interesting proposal and was received positively by the participants.

The participants agreed that the Steering Committee has to:

- Bring together the local associations and institutions committed to facilitating access to housing and to assuring the welfare of the population;
- Become the focal point for sharing experiences and knowledge;
- Update and identify social housing problems, to set a baseline for future actions and

- policies;
- Promote new practises;
 - Maximize resources: the committee should be a way to group entities and help them adopt stronger positions to move ahead with their demands and proposals;
 - Help representatives of the Rimini community to come up with common strategies and work together to develop social housing projects.

4.5 Dissemination activities

The development of the Rimini participatory action has been described in the OIKONET Community Participation blog (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.7. Community participation blog

A brochure (in Italian) summarizing the activities was elaborated and distributed among the participants from Rimini (Figure 4.8).

Figure 4.8. Pages of the brochure (in Italian)

A [video](#) documenting the work done has been produced and published on the project web portal (Figure 4.9).

Figure 4.9. Video describing the action published in YouTube

Finally, the Chamber of Architects of Rimini and Heriscape organized a one-day conference in Rimini, September 27, 2016, on the theme “Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità”. With this opportunity, the outcomes of the participatory action implemented by the two OIKONET partners in Rimini were discussed. The meeting was recorded and it is available in [Youtube](#).

4.6 Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from the experience of designing and implementing the participatory action in Rimini and with regard to the representatives of the Rimini society participating in the actions:

- Each participation process is unique and requires its own particular design process, tools, and methods. For this reason, it is difficult to come up with a generic methodology which can be replicated in different places;
- The interview method is a good tool to get in contact with the specific context and to identify useful information to design the participatory process;
- The round table, in this specific type of action, was an incisive and effective tool: it brings together different entities, institutional or not, and is an opportunity for participants to face issues in a transparent and participatory ways;
- It is important to define shared languages (verbal or graphical) to facilitate the communication and the debate;
- Having a clear idea of the general background and context situation helps to define critical aspects and opportunities: the promoters of the project often cannot figure out solutions, because they do not have the big picture;
- Pushing the participants to work together, to develop project conceived in a system of network is necessary to find a way to solve all the difficulties expressed by the stakeholders;
- For some of the participants, like the Slash association (students' association) a learning space has been created, that will help them to define and consolidate their project of social housing;
- By experiencing the discussion in the round tables, the participants understood the importance of creating a network of institutions, associations, private bodies, etc. to develop, thanks to their integration, effective projects to offer different social housing options;
- Each organization participating in this process is now aware of the activities done by other participants:
- Through the processes designed, the participants learned the importance of sharing knowledge and experiences with each other, to develop stronger proposals;
- The round table helped to create creating a common space fundamental to integrate all the different stakeholders;

5 BRATISLAVA: URBAN WALK IN THE ZEMNÍK AREA

5.1 Introduction

This participatory action was carried out by the municipality of Bratislava, Urban Planning department, from March 2016 to June 2016. The purpose of the action was to gather the views of experts, municipality, residents, general public, community associations and organizations on the development of the area. This work was carried out by a technical team from the municipality.

This chapter describes the structure and the process of the participatory action.

5.2 Process of the participatory action

5.2.1 Designing a participatory process: methods and tools

The aim of this first phase was to identify the groups of stakeholders in the area and analyse and specify the problems, and to organise an urban walk. This was done after a discussion between the municipality and the developer of the project for a national centre of canoeing and rowing in the area of Zemník. As author of the general city master plan, the municipality is responsible for awarding the building permissions.

Several meetings and consultations took place involving members of the city's Urban Planning department (Ing. arch. Karin Lexmann, Ing. arch. Beata Arvayova, Ing. arch. Lubica Fenclova, Mag. rer. nat. Marek Dinka) with the purpose of analysing the problems in the area and setting up the targets of the participatory action in agreement with the general master plan of city of Bratislava (Figures 5.1, 5.2).

Figures 5.1, 5.2. Ing. Arch. Karin Lexmann, Ing. Arch. Beata Arvayova, Mag. rer. nat. Marek Dinka (Urban Planning department, city of Bratislava)

5.2.2 Implementing the participatory process: first joint working sessions

The purpose of this activity was to design a participatory process. The goal was to present the planned development of the Zemník area to all stakeholders, to foster a dialogue between them (Figures 5.3, 5.4).

The following working sessions took place at the municipality:

- 29.3.2016 meeting with Slovak anglers' association, Bratislava V City organization: Martin Sindler, Peter Bozik, Marek Dinka, Lubica Fenclova. The date for the urban walk was agreed at this meeting: 17.5.2016, at 4:00 pm
- 6.4.2016 meeting with the developer of the project, the Slovak association of canoe sprint: Ing. arch. Juraj Fecanin, the author of the urban study, Marek Dinka, Lubica Fenclova. A history of the place, the development project and the future plans were discussed.
- Meeting with Slovak environmental protection group, regional centre in Bratislava: Mgr. Andrej Kovarik, Marek Dinka, Lubica Fenclova. The measures to protect the natural environment, including the alluvial forests around city of Bratislava, were discussed.
- 21.4.2016 examination of the site.
- 10.5.2016 urban walk rehearsal.
-

During these meetings, all of stakeholders had the opportunity to raise the issues which were relevant to them. They were explained on the site during the urban walk.

Figure 5.3. View of the Zemník area

Figure 5.4. Houseboats and dwelling in the area

5.2.3 Evaluating of the inputs obtained in first sessions

The date of the urban walk was fixed for May 17, starting at 4:00 pm. The meeting would start near the access for cars. During the walk it would be explained:

- The history of the locality Zemník.
- The plans for the area according to the Master plan of Bratislava.
- The project for a national centre of canoeing and rowing and its benefits for all stakeholders.
- The nature protection measures which are needed according to the anglers' point of view.
- The nature protection measures to be adopted overall.

5.2.4 Implementing the participatory process: urban walk

An [invitation](#) to attend the urban walk was posted at the webpage of the city of Bratislava (Figure 5.5) and disseminated through the [social web](#) (Figure 5.6). The news was disseminated with the help of local media, mainly in the on-line editions of local newspapers.

Figure 5.5. City of Bratislava's webpage and the invitation for urban walk.

Figure 5.6. Social network – the public event

The walk started in the only available access point: a parking lot situated near buffers under the river boundary bank. The asphalted path along the bank is used by cyclists and it is part of a bike path connecting three countries, Austria, Slovakia and Hungary. The length of the urban walk was approximately 1.5 km (Figure 5.7). The route passed through the alluvial forest of Danube river, then across the river deviation near Bratislava's district of Jarovce and finally along the Zemník's bank.

Komentovaná prechádzka na Zemníku

Figure 5.7. The route of the urban walk

There were four stops during the walk, in which experts gave explanations about the site and the project:

1. Ing. arch. Karin Lexmann, from the city's Urban Planning department, explained the history of the area and its future use as determined in the master plan (Figures 5.8, 5.9).
2. Ing. arch. Juraj Fecanin, from the Slovak association of canoeing, introduced the project for which they asked the building permission (Figures 5.10, 5.11).
3. Martin Sindler, Andrej Bozik, from the Slovak anglers' association, Bratislava V City organization, explained the history and the targets of the environmental protection measures to be applied in the area, from the anglers' point of view (Figures 5.12, 5.13).
4. Mgr. Andrej Kovarik, from the Slovak nature protection group, exposed the reasons to protect the area (Figure 5.14).

At the end of the walk, participants had an opportunity to fulfil a questionnaire about the area of Zemník answering to the following questions:

- How often do you visit the area of Zemník?
- Why do you come here, if you come regularly or occasionally?
- What type of transportation do you use to get to Zemník area?
- What do you think about the future usage of the Zemník area?
- What is your attitude to the planned development in the area of Zemník?
- How would you rate the length of the urban walk (distance)?
- How would you rate the length of the urban walk (time)?
- How would you rate the time of the urban walk (working day at 4:30 PM)?
- How did you find out about the urban walk?

Figures 5.8, 5.9. Karin Lexmann speaks about the master during the urban walk

Figures 5.10, 5.11. Juraj Fecanin speaks about the development and the project of national centre of canoeing and rowing during the urban walk

Figures 5.12, 5.13. Martin Sindler speaks about the history and the targets of the nature protection in the area from the anglers' point of view during the urban walk.

Figure 5.14. Andrej Kovarik speaks about nature protection in context with the development of the Zemník area during the urban walk

5.3 Dissemination activities

The plan of the participatory action has been posted in the “[Community Participation](#)” blog of the OIKONET project (Figure 5.15). A [video reportage](#) of the participatory action is available in OIKONET YouTube channel.

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OIKONET BLOGS Lifelong Learning Programme

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION

HOME PARTICIPATORY ACTIVITIES BARCELONA- Plan RIMINI- Plan BRATISLAVA- Plan SKOPIE- Plan

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BRATISLAVA: Actions

PROCESS OF THE PARTICIPATORY ACTION IN BRATISLAVA: URBAN WALK IN THE ZEMNÍK AREA

4. Implementing the participatory process: urban walk

An invitation to attend the urban walk was posted at the webpage of the city of Bratislava (Figure 4) and disseminated through the social web (Figure 5). The news was disseminated with the help of local media, mainly in the on-line editions of local newspapers.

The walk started in the only available access point: a parking lot situated near buffers under the river boundary bank. The asphalted path along the bank is used by cyclists and it is part of a bike path connecting three countries, Austria, Slovakia and Hungary. The length of the urban walk was approximately 1.5 km (Figure 6). The route passed through the alluvial forest of Danube river, then across the river deviation near Bratislava's district of Jarovce and finally along the Zemník's bank.

Figure 4. City of Bratislava's webpage and the invitation for urban walk

Tweets by @OikonetOrg

Oikonet @OikonetOrg
1st postgraduate @OikonetOrg workshop Global Dwelling, Valencia, 22-23 June 2017. Looking forward to your abstracts goo.gl/MSQRWj

Oikonet @OikonetOrg
Una vecina realojada en los nuevos bloques de #trinitatnova comparte con #prohibit su experiencia

Embed [View on Twitter](#)

Figure 5.15. Community participation blog

A press release after the urban walk was posted at the webpage of the Bratislava municipality (Figure 5.16).

Figure 5.16. Press release at the Bratislava's webpage

Urban walk was also documented and presented by the [Radio Regina](#) (Figure 5.17).

Figure 5.17. Radio Regina website with reportage about the participatory action

6 SKOPJE: A COMMUNITY ACTION IN ILINDEN

6.1 Introduction

6.1.1 Purpose and target group

This is a report of the participatory activity carried out by the School of Architecture, Ss. Cyril & Methodius University, and the municipality of Ilinden, in Skopje, from 15 October 2015 to 17 October 2015. This participatory action was a continuation of the workshop held in Skopje from September 2013 until October 2014, where students and tutors, in collaboration with the local community of Ilinden, gathered information about the living habits of residents, the needs they have, and the kind of spaces they need for community living.

The goal of this second stage of the participatory action has been to recognize and conceptualize the social behaviour around the semiprivate spaces in the neighbourhood. Participants have proposed possible scenarios to carry out social activities.

The municipality has benefited from a research oriented project led by the university. The purpose of the report is to disseminate the work among the members of the OIKONET network, in particular the members of the sub-networks Community Participation.

6.1.2 Contribution of partners

The participatory action in Skopje has been a collaboration between the Faculty of Architecture in Skopje, lecturers from the University of POLIS in Tirana, lecturers from the University of Belgrade and the local authorities and dwellers of the municipality of Ilinden, Skopje. Around 40 students from UKIM, 6 tutors for UKIM, POLIS and AF BELGRADE, and 30 residents, participated in the activities.

6.1.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The ‘Participatory action between residents of Ilinden district, Municipality of Ilinden, Skopje and students from Faculty of Architecture, 2nd session’ was a continuation of the ‘D.2.0 LIVING – DWELLING’, a workshop that also took place in the Municipality of Ilinden, Skopje. In the 1st session the students in collaboration with the local inhabitants have done a social recognition and housing typology research. In the 2nd session they utilized the information gathered and came up with guidelines that helped both the students and the dwellers to better understand of architecture as a tool.

6.2 Living-dwelling

From 15 October 2015 to 17 October 2015, the School of Architecture, Ss. Cyril & Methodius University, in Skopje, and lecturers from Polis University, Tirana, joined the Municipality of Ilinden to carry out a community action project called “Living-Dwelling”. In this action, the students attended lectures and created questionnaires to gather information about the living habits of residents, the needs they have, and the kind of spaces they need for community living. The inhabitants have proposed some potential shared facilities which would be located at these spaces which are partly private, partly public. With the information obtained from the questionnaires, a social map of interactions and usages of the semiprivate spaces has been produced.

The main goal of this participatory action was to foster the collaboration between dwellers and students of architecture in order to identify the needs of the inhabitants. Accordingly, there was a pedagogical goal behind the action, both for students and for dwellers.

For the students of architecture:

- The students learned how to create and use questionnaires as an analytical tool in the process of creating a programme which has social significance for the inhabitants.
- This experience encouraged the students to approach their future professional work as negotiators between dwellers and local authorities.
- Students learned about cohesion through planning/thinking – design by research, which can be adapted according to the needs of the dwellers.

For dwellers:

- The dwellers learned how to live and build/design in correlation with the surrounding.
- Through this participatory action, they were familiarized with the aspect of use of half private space as a zone of social integration between the neighbours.
- An understanding of architecture, not as distinct elements, but as integrated components which function as a whole and observed as a coherent picture.

6.2.1 Description of the case Study

A “rurban” territory is a transition between the city and the country which contains features of both types of settlements but cannot be characterized as one nor the other. A perfect example of this kind of territory is the municipality of Ilinden, which is located 24 km from the city centre. The Municipality has evolved from a village and it was rapidly inhabited during the 1960s by people who migrated from other locations in the country. It has almost orthogonal street pattern and regularly shaped plots. Despite its urban character, rural activities are still noticeable. Because of its diverse natures, it cannot be clearly considered as a part of the city nor a village on its own. These types of settlements mainly adopt the best attributes of both urban and rural living patterns. On the one side, tomatoes grow in the yard, vineyards cover the thresholds to the house, and kids play football on the streets. On the other side, all the houses are arranged in regular rectangular blocks (Figure 6.1), public transportation reaches the area and there are supermarkets nearby. The streets are stuck in the middle, they are asphalted, but narrow, cars can be seen, but they run slowly, there are no sidewalks, but the street is the pedestrian area (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.1. Urban fragment from the Ilinden neighbourhood

Figure 6.2. Neighbourhood of Ilinden

6.3 Learning Activities

Students in close cooperation with citizens and local administration examined the existing dwelling and living patterns of the neighbourhood focusing on the residential urban blocks. The participatory action lasted one week. During this time students carried out the following tasks:

Phase 1: Theoretical background. Students attended an opening ceremony at the Faculty of Architecture in Skopje followed by lectures which introduced them to the site and to the object of the research.

Phase 2: Site visit. The theoretical discussion moved to the hall of the municipality of Ilinden (Figure 6.3).

Figure 6.3. Presentation at the city hall

Phase 3: Meeting with the neighbours. The most important part of a participatory action is to bring different stakeholders together. Students met dwellers to get first-hand knowledge of their needs for social interaction, and to find out possible usages for the semiprivate spaces (Figure 6.4).

Figure 6.4. Students surveying the area in contact with residents

Phase 4: Preparing a questionnaire. Based on the information gathered on the site, students prepared questionnaires covering different areas of interest. The previous meeting between students and dwellers helped them to identify relevant questions.

Phase 5: Collecting data from the questionnaires. Each group of students collected and analysed the data obtained from the questionnaires and then represented graphically the answers (Figure 6.5).

Figure 6.5. Map of usages of the semi-private zones

Phase 6: Creating sociograms. Students created sociograms to represent the actual social interactions in the neighbourhood at different scales (Figure 6.6)

Figure 6.6. Sociogram of shared semi-private spaces

Phase 7: Producing GIF and video files. A set of animated GIF and video files have been produced, based on the sociograms (Figure 6.7).

Figure 6.7. A frame from the map of shared semi-private spaces

6.4 Dissemination activities

The development of the Skopje participatory action has been described in the OIKONET Community Participation blog (Figure 6.8)

Figure 6.8. Community participation blog

6.5 Conclusions

The main challenge of the community participation action carried out in Ilinden was to grasp the multiple perceptions about the potential of the semi-private spaces. The results of the conducted survey highlighted the importance of public spaces in creating a more socially sustainable community. The survey also showed that most of the residents understood the yard as a private space attached to their home. Every inhabitant uses their yard differently. Unlike from the private house which is a domain of intimacy and has a specific form, the yard is characterized by the event which happens in space and time and it does not have a fixed formal expression. The dynamism and mutability of the semi-private spaces is a direct manifestation of the social interactions.

The students have learned how to create and use surveys as tools to analyse the social dynamics of a community. Furthermore, they were confronted with the reality of people living in rural areas and they had to learn how to communicate with the dwellers. Students also became acquainted with the urban planning legislation and procedures and took them into account in their proposals.

Through the community participation action, the dwellers became aware that semi-private spaces are places for social interaction. The action has helped to create a sense of community by bringing the dwellers together in discussions about the future urban development. Along this process, dwellers have learnt to better comprehend urban plans and the role of the local administration in planning. On the other hand, the municipal authorities have become more sensitive to the importance of the contributions of citizens.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The four community actions have embraced different scales of the built environment: from the private, domestic scale (Barcelona, Rimini) to the public urban scale (Bratislava), including semi-private spaces between both scales (Skopje). Two of the actions have involved students from architecture and planning schools (Barcelona, Skopje). Citizens have participated in the action in Barcelona (members of a cohousing cooperative), Skopje (neighbours), and Bratislava (users of the Zemník area). Civic society actors have been involved in the search for solutions for the social housing shortage in Rimini. The participatory actions in Bratislava and Rimini have been led by the municipal administrations.

The participatory actions have provided an opportunity to devise and implement strategies to involve different stakeholder groups in decision making processes that have an impact on their living environment, at various scales. It remains to be verified though the extent to which these actions can contribute to a real transformation of the existing power structures governing in each decision making realm.